

Figure Z11

Figure Z11: Deconvolved cell type proportion changes with high-fat diet and exercise training. (A-C) Sample-specific proportions of different cell types/groups after bulk RNA-seq data deconvolution across the four intervention groups in scWAT **(A)**, vWAT **(B)**, and skeletal muscle **(C)**. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.